

Importance of Dependency on Local Area for Backbone Regular Courses - A Case Study

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This paper shows the importance of dependency on local area for admissions. The paper is a case study on one of the premium institute of Punjab. Different technical and non technical courses available in the Institute are divided into 04 categories A, B, C & D depends on the present demand. In order to achieve desirable admission target in local area, the Institute teams have to covered 70 km distance by radius from the location of the Institute. Further, distance of the Institute from various feeder areas is calculated and admission target given to teams not only to cover courses in category C & D but also in Category A & B. This paper is not having more reference because it is based on the true data collected on various parameters.

Keywords: local area, admission, lateral entry, aicte, pci, punjab

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1. Introduction

In this case study, the author worked on various parameters required to obtain a good number of admissions especially in technical courses available. This case study is performed on one of the best Institutes of Punjab. The Institute is running 37 courses with 2880 Intake plus students admitted in 2nd year through Lateral Entry (LEET). The author collected the data based on available courses; distribute the available courses in 04 categories based on demand and also checked the distance of the Institute from various feeder areas so that the Institute teams can make strategy and planning to cover maximum areas.

2. Courses Available and its Eligibility

The Institute provides education in technical and non-technical courses affiliated with different State Universities, All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE), Pharmacy Council of India (PCI), Technical State Board, Nursing Councils, Bar Council etc. The Institute provides 37 courses in Engineering, Management, Pharmacy, Law, Allied, Agriculture, Nursing, Education (B.Ed) etc. The list of available courses with eligibility criteria is shown in Table 1. Further Table 1 also shows that how many courses the students can opt after completing particular education e.g. after 10th students can opt for 05 courses, after 10+2 (Arts) student can opt for 05 courses and so on.

Table 1: Eligibility of various courses

Eligibility	For Courses	Courses Offered
Matric	Diploma, Home based Care Helper, OT attended, Ambulance attended, Hospital & Home care attended	05
Any 10+2 (Arts)	Diploma, BBA, BCA, ANM, GNM	05
10+2 (Commerce)	B.Com (Hons.), Diploma, BBA	03
10+2 (Voc.) Technical	Diploma (LEET), BCA, BBA, B. Com (H)	04
10+2 (Voc.) (MLS/MLT)	B.Sc (RMIT), B. Sc (MLS), B. Sc (Respiratory Care Technology), B. Sc (Anesthesia Technology), B. Sc (Dialysis Technology), B. Sc (Cardiac care technology), BCA, BBA, B, Com (H)	09

10+2 (Non Medical)	Diploma (LEET), B.Tech, D. Pharma, B. Pharma, BSc (RMIT), B.Sc (NM), B. Sc (Bio tech.), B.Sc (MLS), B. Sc (Agriculture), B. Sc (Anesthesia), B. Sc (Cardiac care technology), B. Sc (Respiratory Care Technology), B. Sc (Anesthesia Technology), B. Sc (Dialysis Technology).	13
10+2 (Medical)	B. Sc (Nursing), GNM, D. Pharma, B. Pharma, B.Sc (RMIT), B.Sc (OTT), B. Sc (RIT), B. Sc (Bio tech.), B.Sc (MLS), B. Sc (Agriculture), B. Sc (Anesthesia), B. Sc (Cardiac care technology), B. Sc (Respiratory Care Technology), B. Sc (Anesthesia Technology), B. Sc (Dialysis Technology).	14
ITI	Diploma	01
Diploma (Engineering)	B. Tech, BCA, BBA	03
Any B. Tech	M.Tech, LLB	02
B. Tech (CSE/IT)	M. Tech, MCA	02
BCA	MCA	01
B.Sc (CSE/IT)	MCA	01
Any Graduation (With Maths)	MCA	01
GNM	B. Sc (N) Post Basic	01
B.Sc (NM)	M.Sc (Chem., Phy, Maths)	01
B. Sc (with Maths)	B. Tech	01
Any Graduation	MBA, B. Ed, LLB	03
Graduation (Commerce/ Business Management/ Management)	M.Com.	01
D. Pharmacy	B. Pharmacy (LEET), B. Sc (MLS), B. Sc (RIT)	03
Diploma RIT	B. Sc (RIT)	01
Diploma (Anesthesia)	B. Sc (Anesthesia)	01
Diploma (Cardiac Care)	B. Sc (Cardiac Care)	01
Diploma (Respiratory)	B. Sc (Respiratory)	01
Diploma (Dialysis Technology)	B. Sc (Dialysis Technology)	01
Diploma (RMIT)	B. Sc (RMIT)	01
Diploma (OTT)	B. Sc (OTT)	01
Diploma (MLS/MLT)	B. Sc (MLS)	01
B. Sc (MLS)	M.Sc (MLS)	01

3. Category wise Distribution of Courses

The author distributed these 37 courses in four categories as per the present course demand in 2024-25. These categories are given in table 2:

a. Backbone regular courses: These courses are the backbone of any Institutes. Without these courses no Institute will survive. As per present scenario, the author selected 11 courses in this category which includes B.Tech, M. Tech, Diploma in Engineering, B.Sc (Non medical), B. Sc (Bio Tech.), B. Sc (Agriculture), MBA, M.Sc (Physics, Chemistry, Maths), M.Com (H).

b. Hide and seek courses: Due to lack of awareness of such courses Institute have to search for the students. As per present scenario, the author selected 09 courses in this category which includes B.Sc (Anesthesia Tech.), B.Sc (Dialysis Tech.), B.Sc (Cardiac Care), B.Sc (Respiratory Care), B. Sc (RMIT), B.Sc (Operation theater technician), B.Sc (RIT), B.Sc (MLS), M.Sc (MLS).

c. Hot cake courses: These are such courses in which present demand is at its maximum and students themselves approach the institute for admission. Institutes tried to get good students who will complete their courses within time with good grades. The author has selected 13 courses in this category includes ANM, GNM, B. Sc (Nursing), B. Sc (Nursing) Post Basic, B.Ed, LLB, BA LLB, D. Pharmacy, B. Pharmacy, BBA, BCA, B. Com (H) & MCA.

d. Non technical skilled courses: These are non technical skilled courses which provide direct job opportunities after 06 months. It includes 04 courses home based care helper, OT attended, Ambulance attendance, Hospital and home care attended.

Table 2: Distribution of 1st year and LEET courses in various categories in 2024-25

Category	Category	No of Courses	1st Year	Vacant for LEET	Total Vacant for 2025-26
A	Backbone Regular Courses	11	1380	602	1982
B	Hide & Seek Courses	09	330	171	501
C	Hot cake courses	13	1090	19	1109
D	Non Technical Skilled Courses	04	80	Nil	80
	Total	37	2880	792	3672

3.1 Category A (Backbone Regular Courses)

Table 3 shows the Intake of students in first year and In second year through lateral entry (LEET). The number of seats in LEET is not fixed, it is calculated as 10% of 1st year intake plus number of vacant or dropout seats in first year. Eg In 1st year 50 seats are filled out of 60 intakes. So in 2nd year total seats which can be filled through LEET are 06 (10% of 1st year intake) plus 10 i.e 16. We have considered demand of courses, distance from Institute, and some factors in calculating the minimum seats required to be filled in 2025-26 for the survival of the Institute.

Table 3: Intake of Category A courses (Backbone regular courses)

S. No	Courses with Intake	1st Year	LEET	Total	Minimum Required to be Filled in 2025-26
1	B.Tech	540	377	917	382
2	M.Tech	120	NIL	120	36
3	Diploma	240	225	465	227
4	B. Sc (NM)	60	NIL	60	30
5	B. Sc (Bio. tech)	60	NIL	60	30
6	B. Sc (Agriculture)	60	Nil	60	40
7	MBA	180	Nil	180	120
8	M.Sc Physics	30	Nil	30	16
9	M. Sc Chemistry	30	Nil	30	16
10	M. Sc Maths	30	Nil	30	15
11	M.Com (H)	30	Nil	30	18

3.1.1 Engineering

The Institute is offering B.Tech in 08 branches with total intake of 540 seats. It includes Electrical Engg. (EE), Mechanical Engg. (ME), Computer Science & Engineering (CSE), Civil Engg., Electronics and Communication Engg. (ECE), Food Technology (FT), Information technology (IT) & Artificial Intelligence (AI). The basic qualification required to do B. Tech is 10+2 (NM). As B. Tech is the back bone of any technical Institute but as per present scenario it is not an easy task to reach to satisfactory level in certain branches of B. Tech, so expected admissions in each branch is given in table 4, it is required to fill 340 seats out of 540. This target is distributed among various admission teams working in different areas. As per B. Tech LEET is concerned its basic qualification is Diploma, their only 4 -5 polytechnics available in and around 70 km range. So it is expected to have around 42 admissions through LEET.

The basic eligibility for doing M. Tech is B. Tech. The Institute is offering M. Tech in 06 branches with total intake of 120 students. Diploma is also backbone of the Institute. The basic eligibility of diploma 1st Year is 10th, 10+2 (Arts, Commerce) and in LEET it is 10+2 NM, ITI, 10+2 Vocational. As per the present scenario, it is expected to fill 190 seats in 1st year diploma and around 40 in diploma LEET. The reason for filling lower seats through LEET in diploma is non availability of ITI eligible students especially in CSE, ECE and Civil.

Table 4: Total intake in B.Tech and minimum required admissions in 2025-26

B. Tech with Intake	EE	ME	CIVIL	CSE	ECE	IT	FT	AIML
First year Intake (540)	60	60	60	150	60	30	60	60
Minimum required admissions in first year	40	30	30	125	15	20	40	40
Minimum expected admissions in LEET	10	05	05	20	02	00	00	00

Table 5: Total intake in M. Tech and minimum required admissions in 2025-26

M. Tech with Intake	EE	ME	CIVIL	CSE	ECE	FT
Intake (120)	18	18	18	24	24	18
Minimum required admissions	8	5	5	12	2	4

Table 6: Total intake in Diploma and minimum required admissions in 2025-26

Diploma with Intake	EE	ME	CIVIL	CSE	ECE
First year Intake (300)	60	60	60	60	60
Minimum required admissions in first year	60	35	35	45	15
Minimum required admissions in LEET	10	10	08	07	02

3.1.2 Courses with 10+2 (Non Medical) Eligibility

There are many courses running in the Institute whose basic eligibility is 10+2 (NM) i.e. Tech, Diploma (LEET), D. Pharma, B. Pharma, B.Sc (RMIT), B.Sc (NM), B. Sc (Bio tech.), B.Sc (MLS), B.Sc (Agriculture), B. Sc (Cardiac), B. Sc (Respiratory), B. Sc (Anesthesia), B. Sc (Dialysis) etc. The B.Sc (NM), B. Sc (Bio tech.), B. Sc (Agriculture) are selected in the category A (shown in table 7) and admissions required for these three in totality is around 100. The courses with same eligibility can create internal competition within the Institute. It is analyzed from various sources that number of students opted for Non medical in 10+1 and 10+2 is continuously decreasing from last few years.

Table 7: Bachelor level courses in Category A

Course with Intake	B. Sc (NM)	B. Sc (Biotech)	B.Sc (Agriculture)	Total
Intake	60	60	60	180
Minimum Required Admissions	30	30	40	100

3.1.3 Master Level Courses

Master level courses such as MBA, M.Sc. (Chemistry, Physics, Math's), M. Com (Hons.) are included in category A. The eligibility of MBA is any graduation and for M.Sc (Chemistry, Physics) eligibility is B. Sc (Non Medical /Medical) but for M.Sc (Maths) it is B.Sc (NM) and for M. Com (H) eligibility is graduation (With Commerce/ Management/ Business Management). There is large number of colleges providing graduation courses in arts and commerce but B.Sc (NM/M) is available in few colleges. As per present scenario, the minimum number of seats in Master level of Category A is required to be filled in 2025-26 is around 185 seats as given in table 8.

Table 8: Master level courses in Category A

Course with Intake	MBA	MSc (Physics)	MSc (Chemistry)	MSc (Maths)	M. Com (H)	Total
Intake	180	30	30	30	30	300
Minimum required Admissions	120	16	16	15	18	185

3.2 Category B (Hide & Seek Courses)

The courses distributed under category B are listed in table 9. The eligibility of these courses in 1st year is 10+2 (Non medical/ Medical). A student who have passed non medical in 10+2 is eligible to take admission in more than 10 courses available. As per present scenario only around 10% of the students opting for non medical as compared to arts, it means we have created internal competition for non medical students. This internal competition badly affects the courses in Category A. With this strategy, none of the courses with non medical as its basic qualification can be filled. So we have to ensure that students with medical background can only take admission in category B courses. As per present scenario, students belong to other states such as J&K is opted for these courses. In addition to dependency on other states, we need to create awareness among local students also so that they can opt Category B courses.

Moreover, it is not an easy task to distribute each course of category B in area wise individually so we tried to combined some courses of category B and distribute in different areas shown in table 15 & 16.

For admission through Lateral Entry (LEET) in category B courses i.e. B. Sc (Anesthesia), B. Sc (Dialysis), B. Sc (Cardiac Care), B. Sc (Respiratory Care), B. Sc (RMIT), B.Sc (MLS), B. Sc OTT, basic eligibility is diploma in same course, but some course can also take students with 10+2 (Voc.) in MLS/MLT, D. Pharmacy etc. Moreover, it is also found that diploma in same field are not easily available so it may be a tough task to fill LEET seats of category B.

Table 9: Category B (Hide & seek courses)

S. No	Courses with Intake	1st Year	Vacant in LEET	Total	Minimum Required to be Filled in 1st year in 2025-26
1	B.Sc Anesthesia (Tech.)	30	25	55	22
2	B.Sc (Dialysis Tech.)	30	28	58	22
3	B.Sc (Cardiac Care)	30	19	49	22
4	B.Sc Respiratory (Care)	30	32	62	22
5	B.Sc (RMIT)	30	13	43	18
6	B.Sc (OTT)	30	11	41	20
7	B. Sc (RIT)	60	Nil	60	18
8	B. Sc (MLS)	60	43	103	35
9	M. SC (MLS)	30	Nil	30	15

3.3 Category C (Hot Cake Courses)

The courses under category C is considered as hot cake courses. Hot cake courses are those courses which are in demand and students themselves approach the Institutes for admissions. More than 90 to 95% seats are filled in these courses. The interested students may come from any part within 70 km or outside 70 km. So admission teams are not required to put much effort to attract these students. It is expected to fill more than 70% available seats without much effort. The only efforts required in this category are awareness about the courses in local area. So these courses are not possible to distribute according to different areas. Table 10 shows courses in Category C.

Table 10: Category C (Hot cake courses)

S. No	Courses with Intake	1st Year	LEET	Total
1	ANM	30	Nil	30
2	GNM	60	Nil	60
3	B.Sc (Nursing)	60	Nil	60
4	B. Sc (N) Post Basic	30	Nil	30
5	B.Ed.	100	Nil	100
6	LLB	120	Nil	120
7	BA LLB	180	Nil	180
8	D. Pharmacy	60	Nil	60
9	B. Pharmacy	60	07	67
10	BBA	90	Nil	90
11	BCA	120	12	132
12	B. Com (H)	120	Nil	120
13	MCA	60	Nil	60

3.4 Category D (Non Technical Skilled Courses)

The courses considered under Category D are non technical skilled courses listed in table 11. The basic eligibility of these courses is metric. It is expected that the person who required job after 6 months can preferred these courses. It is also not required to be distributing these courses area wise.

Table 11: Category D (Non-technical skilled courses)

S. No	Courses	Total
1	Home based Care Helper	20
2	OT Attended	20
3	Ambulance Attendance	20
4	Hospital & Home care attended	20

4. Influential Local Areas to be Covered

In order to achieve the best results in terms of admission, the admission teams have to be covered 70 km distance by radius from the location of the Institute. The areas covered under radius of 70 km are shown in table 12 and in figure 1.

Figure 1: Areas covered under radius of 70 km from Institute

Table 12: Area wise distance from Institute within 70 km radius

S.No	Area	Distance from Institute
1	Nabha	29 km
2	Patran	47 km
3	Moonak	71 km
4	Khanauri	63 km
5	Dirba	30 km
6	Cheema	37 km
7	Patiala	48 km
8	Barnala	56 km
9	Tappa	69 km
10	Dhanaula	43 km
11	Malerkotla	39 km
12	Dhuri	22 km
13	Bhawanigarh	10 km
14	Sangrur	12 km
15	Sunam	24 km
16	Lehragagga	50 km
17	Longowal	40 km
18	Samana	32 km
19	Ahmedgarh	60 km
20	Amargarh	30 km
21	Bareta	70 km
22	Within 15 km	Within 15 km
23	Mansa	68 km

The minimum area wise seats of Category A and B, required to be filled in 2025-26 are shown in table 13, 14, 15 and 16. The content in table 13 to 16 is based on number of schools available; distance from the Institute, transport facility provided by the Institute, professional Competitors in particular area and approachability & connectivity of the students.

Table 13: Distance wise (1 to 11) admission target for Category A courses

Course	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
B.Tech	25	7	5	5	8	5	25	15	5	5	25
B. Tech- LEET	4	2	2	2	0	0	10	3	0	0	3
M.Tech	2	1	1	1	1	1	5	2	0	0	2
Diploma	12	5	3	3	10	5	12	10	3	3	15
Diploma LEET	4	1	0	0	2	1	4	2	0	0	4
B. Sc (NM), B. Sc (Bio tech), B. Sc Agriculture	6	3	1	1	3	4	8	4	1	3	6
MBA	8	2	2	2	4	2	10	5	2	2	15
M.Sc (Physics, Chem. Maths)	3	1	1	1	2	1	6	4	0	1	4
M.Com (Hons.)	2	1	0	0	1	1	2	2	0	1	2
Total	66	23	15	15	31	20	82	47	11	15	76

Table 14: Distance wise (12 to 23) admission target for Category A courses

Course	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
B.Tech	20	20	35	25	10	5	10	1	5	5	40	5
B. Tech- LEET	3	3	8	3	2	2	2	0	2	1	10	1
M.Tech	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	0	1	1	4	1
Diploma	15	20	25	20	5	5	5	2	10	2	25	3
Diploma LEET	2	3	4	2	0	0	1	0	1	0	4	0
B. Sc (NM), B. Sc (Bio tech), B. Sc Agriculture	6	4	10	4	1	3	3	1	2	1	15	1
MBA	5	5	20	4	2	1	2	1	5	1	20	1
M.Sc (Physics, Chem. Maths)	2	2	6	2	1	1	2	0	1	0	10	0
M.Com (Hons.)	2	2	4	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	5	0
Total	56	60	114	63	22	19	28	5	28	12	133	12

Table 15: Distance wise (1 to 11) admission target for Category B courses

Course	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
B. Sc (Anesthesia/ Dialysis/ Cardiac care/ Respiratory Care)	3	1	1	1	1	2	5	3	1	1	4
B.Sc (RMIT/ RIT/MLS/OTT)	6	3	2	2	2	5	3	1	1	4	
M. Sc (MLS)	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	
Total	10	4	3	3	3	4	11	7	2	2	9

Table 16: Distance wise (12 to 23) admission target for Category B courses

Course	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
B. Sc (Anesthesia/ Dialysis/ Cardiac care/ Respiratory Care)	3	3	4	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	10	1
B.Sc (RMIT/ RIT/MLS/OTT)	2	2	6	2	1	1	1	0	1	0	10	0
M. Sc (MLS)	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	0
Total	6	6	12	5	3	3	4	1	3	1	22	1

In table 17, proposed area wise target of all courses under category A & B is mentioned. The courses under C are in demand and students themselves approach the Institutes for admissions. The interested students may come from any part within 70 km or outside 70 km. So admission teams are not required to put many efforts to attract these students. It is expected to fill more than 70% available seats without much effort. There is also not required to put efforts for category D courses. Table 17 shows that Nabha team will fill minimum 66 students in courses under Category A, 10 students in Category B and no limit for students in category C & D and so on.

Table 17: Proposed area wise target of all categories

S. No	Area	Category A	Category B	Category C	Category D	Total
1	Nabha	66	10			76
2	Patran	23	4			27
3	Moonak	15	3			18
4	Khanauri	15	3			18
5	Dirba	31	3			34
6	Cheema	20	4			24
7	Patiala	82	11			93
8	Barnala	47	7			54
9	Tappa	11	2			13
10	Dhanaula	15	2			17
11	Malerkotla	76	9			85
12	Dhuri	56	6			62
13	Bhawanigarh	60	6			66
14	Sangrur	114	12			126
15	Sunam	63	5			68
16	Lehragagga	22	3			25
17	Longowal	19	3			22
18	Samana	28	4			32
19	Ahmedgarh	05	1			6
20	Amargarh	28	3			31
21	Bareta	12	1			13
22	All Areas within 15 km	133	22			155
23	Mansa	12	1			13

5. Present Situation of Technical Education

With reference to AICTE Web portal, in India AICTE is running 399 diploma levels, 53 Post diploma levels, 520 Post graduate (PG) levels, 12 PG diploma level & 234 under graduate (UG) level technical courses. From last few years, number of Engineering & Technology Institutions is continuously decreasing in India and also in Punjab as shown in table 18.

Table 18: Approved institutions as per AICTE

Year	In India	In Punjab
2019-20	6,176	218
2020-21	6,062	204
2021-22	5,935	190
2022-23	5,878	174
2023-24	5,868	163

Table 19 shows that from 2019 to 2021, Intake in UG & diploma courses decreases but from 2022 onwards it starts increasing. The demand of all PG level courses in continually decreasing from last few years.

Table 19: Approved intake of various technical courses as per AICTE in India

Year	UG	PG Dip.	PG Cert.	PG	Post Diploma	Diploma	Total
2019-20	13,28,247	1,894	120	1,66,208	3,476	10,39,767	25,39,712
2020-21	12,86,545	1,766	120	1,45,939	3,113	10,05,435	24,42,918
2021-22	12,54,507	1,850	xx	1,35,128	2,825	9,74,280	23,68,590
2022-23	12,74,190	1,745	60	1,28,466	2,796	9,68,166	23,75,423
2023-24	13,52,639	1,595	110	1,23,651	2,671	10,25,413	25,04,079

Table 20 shows that in Punjab demand of UG, diploma and PG level courses in continually decreasing since 2019-20.

Table 20: Approved intake of various technical courses as per AICTE in Punjab

Year	UG	PG Certificate	PG	Post Diploma	Diploma	Total
2019-20	32,530	120	3,351	230	42,287	78,518
2020-21	28,999	120	2,798	170	35,924	68,011
2021-22	28,069	60	2,591	110	32,014	62,844
2022-23	24,718	60	2,553	140	28,976	56,247
2023-24	22,715	60	2,059	140	24,059	49,033

Table 21 shows that the demand of UG courses and diploma is improved from last 2 years at all India level but in Punjab it is still decreasing from last few years. It also shows that the demand for other PG courses is still decreasing continuously at all levels.

Table 21: Approved intake and enrollment in courses

Institute Type	UG		PG		Diploma	
	Intake	Enrol.	Intake	Enrol.	Intake	Enrol.
2019-20	1328067	740881	168402	62748	1043243	617607
2020-21	1286725	728443	147789	62832	1008404	520133
2021-22	1254507	696439	136978	54096	977045	554690
2022-23	1274190	1035977	130271	44269	970902	651796
2023-24	1350639		125356		1028024	

6. Observation

The author worked at various senior positions in reputed Institutes of Punjab since 20 years and monitoring the admission scenario very closely. From last 6-7 years, it is found that the admission process especially in technical institutes is totally changed. Special teams have been constituted by Institutes not only to cover local areas, but also to cover other states and contact International students. The Institutes heavily invested to stay alive in market.

The Institute teams must focus on some following important parameters.

1. Institute needs to understand the importance of local market and required to design marketing strategy to cover 70 km of local area and ensure to cover each school, college, tuition centers, villages, etc. within 70 km radius.
2. Regularly update list of schools covering 70 km radius around the Institute. More than 75% of the total admissions are required to come from area within 70 km range.
3. The list includes all government and Private schools of both PSEB, CBSE teaching upto 10th & 10+2 level.
4. Regularly update list of teaching staff involved in especially with Science, Maths, Vocational, ITI, Principals, and other influential members related with Schools.
5. Also cover other states and countries like Nepal, Bangladesh, Sudan etc., but the dependency on outside areas need to be reduced.

6. To cover local area, the Institute team's must collectively work with all stakeholders including faculty, staff, students, parents, and all other persons directly and indirectly associated with the Institute. Special lucrative Incentive schemes for all stakeholders need to be introduced.

7. Transportation plays a crucial role in promoting the goodwill of the Institute. So its routes should be regularly updated.

8. Minimum area wise target as given in table 17 should be given by the Director/ Chairman to the admission teams working in particular area.

9. It is not fare practice that admission team's work on the hot cake category C only as courses in this category is already in demand so students themselves approach the Institute. The main focus of the team is on courses in category A & B.

10. Belongings between management, faculty and students in utmost important.

11. Another major problem faced by an Institution is non availability of students. The students are least interested to enroll in 10+2 (NM).

12. All Admission teams shared their experiences after every 15 days covering past experience, present problems with solutions & future admission activities.

13. Training to all marketing & calling team is most important.

14. We have to target the educated parents with technical background, with particular job timing etc.

15. To maintain the reputation of the Institute through word of Mouth.

16. Provide awareness of Govt. Policies, University Schemes, and Scholarships etc.

17. Regularly updation on Social Media, on Institute website, maintains public Relations.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, Importance of dependency on local area has been analyzed. In this paper, the courses available in the Institute are categorized in category A, B, C & D along with its eligibility criteria. In order to achieve desirable admission target in local area, the Institute teams have to covered 70 km distance by radius from the location of the Institute with collective efforts from all stakeholders. The area wise target given to teams by management. As courses in Category A are the backbone of technical Institute so the teams must work on category A and B courses.

The courses under category C is considered as hot cake courses which are in demand and students themselves approach the Institutes for admissions. The interested students may come from any part within 70 km or outside 70 km. So admission teams are not required to put much effort to attract these students.

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